

THE INSTITUTION OF ENGINEERS OF IRELAND

WEXFORD MAIN DRAINAGE SCHEME

Edward FitzGerald, BE, CEng, MIEI, MCIWEM, MICE.
Director, T.J.O'Connor & Associates

Diarmuid Cahalane, BE, MEng Sc, CEng, MIEI, MCIWEM.
Associate, T.J.O'Connor & Associates.

Glenbeigh Records
Management

F3265124

Paper presented to The Institution of Engineers of Ireland and The Chartered Institution of Water and Environmental Management,
Republic of Ireland Branch on 21st February 2000.

SYNOPSIS

Wexford Main Drainage Scheme is a £45 million project designed to upgrade the pipe network, to eliminate the discharge of untreated sewage to Wexford Harbour and to reduce the frequency of tidal flooding in the town centre area. This paper describes the construction works completed to date on the collection system, pumping stations and interceptor sewer as well as mathematical and physical modelling undertaken for the quay extension reclamation works and for the main lift pumping station at Trinity Street. The impact of the works on Wexford Harbour and the measures adopted to mitigate environmental impacts are also addressed.

WEXFORD MAIN DRAINAGE SCHEME

FIGURE 1

INTRODUCTION

The town of Wexford is situated in the south east of the County of Wexford where the river Slaney broadens out to form the large shallow body of water known as Wexford Harbour. Wexford has a long maritime tradition being a significant trading harbour up until the early years of this century, when the silting of the channel through the Harbour became excessive. Some sources argue that this was attributable in part to the reclamation of the North and South Slobbs in the 19th Century. Attempts had been made, when the situation first became a problem, to secure a channel to the open sea through the construction of training walls but funds for their construction quickly ran out.

Wexford and its environs had a population of 16500 persons at

the 1996 census. The domestic foul sewage and industrial wastewaters from Wexford Town and its environs discharge through as many as twenty five separate outfalls into the Harbour many of which are directly in front of Wexford Quays. Because of these untreated discharges, the entire quay front area is grossly polluted and deficient in aesthetic and amenity value. Unsightly floating solids are visible on the surface of the water, offensive odours arise from the sewage and thick foam and tainted colour are visible over large areas of the Quay front.

Planning for the Wexford Main Drainage Scheme commenced in 1978. A comprehensive Interim Report was prepared by T.J. O'Connor & Associates in 1979 which proposed a 30 year plan to be completed in 3 phases. The Main Drainage Scheme, as envisaged in the Interim Report, was intended to address the inadequacies in the existing system. These inadequacies have been identified as follows:

- i. Most of the existing sewerage network in the town was in bad structural condition
- ii. Some areas of the town were susceptible to flooding, due to the indiscriminate use of storm overflows, discharging excess flows from one sewer to another - the capacities of the relieving sewers being inadequate to carry the extra flow.
- iii. Wastewater was being discharged untreated from the drainage area directly into the harbour and at the mouth of the River Slaney thereby causing nuisance and pollution of the receiving waters.
- iv. Tidal flooding of the quayfront and the streets leading to the quays was occurring at least once or twice a year.

PRELIMINARY REPORT

The Preliminary Report for the first phase of the Scheme was prepared by T.J.O'Connor & Associates in 1983. This Report had the following objectives:-

- i. To review Phase 1 of the three phase drainage programme set out in the Interim Report of August 1979; maintaining the general objectives therein, updating the design parameters where appropriate and considering in detail the construction of a quay extension in which to lay the interceptor pipeline.
- ii. To review the necessity for treatment of waterborne waste prior to discharge into Wexford Harbour in the light of findings of a report by An Foras Forbartha, "Dispersion and Water Quality in Wexford Harbour and Slaney Estuary" produced, in 1980.
- iii. To present the findings and analysis of a subsoil investigation undertaken in April/May 1983
- iv. to project a phasing programme on the recommended scheme based on estimated costs.

The drainage areas for the overall Wexford Main Drainage Scheme encompasses all developed areas of the town and areas which development is envisaged within the Bishopswater catchment which extends to the west of the town, see Figure 1. The Carcur catchment to the northeast of the town drains to the Carcur pumping station and was not originally included in the Main Drainage Scheme. It is a distinct catchment and is the subject of a Preliminary Report which is in preparation at present. The sewage flows from the Carcur catchment will be pumped into the Main Drainage system for onward conveyance to the proposed sewage treatment works. Sewers serving Sinnotstown to the south of the town and the adjoining I.D.A. industrial estate have also been added to the Main Drainage Scheme in recent years. Proposals for a sewerage system serving development on the north side of Wexford Bridge at Crosstown Ferrybank have also been developed in a separate Preliminary Report. Sewage flows from here will also be pumped into the Main Drainage Scheme

The total area of the Bishopswater catchment is approximately 690

WEXFORD MAIN DRAINAGE SCHEME

FIGURE 5

the floor of the sump and the intake of the storm pumps was clearly evident under the proposed operating conditions. Sub-surface (forced) vortices are formed by flow and rotation and their formation beneath propeller pump intakes has been studied extensively by ABS Pumps, the pump suppliers, who recommended that the wall behind the pump intakes be profiled and that the floor beneath the pumps be roughened. These revisions were incorporated in the model and the problem of sub surface vortices were eliminated. With the revised layout of the sump the flow distribution to each of the storm pumps was reasonably uniform and dead zones appeared to be minimum. This final layout formed the basis for the Civil Works design which is shown at Figure 5.

Pumping Stations - Civil Works Design.

An extensive site investigation was undertaken in respect of the Quay Pumping Station with boreholes

drilled by IGSL in 1986 and again in 1996/97. The Quay Pumping Station is located on a site between Trinity Street and the Railway line at the Southern end of Wexford Quay. The general ground level on the site is 4.7m to 5m OD. The tidal variation in Wexford Harbour is 3.13m OD MHWST down to 1.63m OD MLWST although tides as high as 4.4m OD were recorded during the course of the Pipelines Contract No. 1. (January 1996). The site of the pumping station had been reclaimed from the sea (probably after 1840) and was formerly the Wexford South Station on the Dublin Rosslare railway line. Also, a Gasworks was located on or close to the site in the past.

The stratification of the site is confused, partly due to the reclamation of the land, but also due to the weathered nature of the bedrock which sometimes cannot be distinguished from a very stiff cohesive fill. The upper strata to about +0.5m OD to -1.5m OD

comprises fill and soft/loose organic silts and loose sands. These overlie medium dense/dense gravels and firm to very stiff sandy silt and boulder clays to about -3.5m OD. The soil/rocks below that level comprise possible very stiff cohesive tills, dense gravels or weathered rock. The sump dimensions are 10.7m x 16m internally with a depth to formation of 11 metres. Pumping tests were undertaken by IGSL to establish groundwater drawdown associated with potential dewatering. The geotechnical considerations relevant to the proposed development included method of construction of the pumping station, the effects of ground water lowering and of the construction on the buildings and adjacent railway together with uplift considerations both during construction and on the finished structure.

The scheme went to tender based on a monolithic watertight reinforced concrete structure including base slab walls and suspended slab at ground level within a perimeter secant piled wall. The secant piled wall was intended to contribute additional weight towards the resistance of buoyancy uplift on the substructure.

The Contractor was entitled to offer alternatives to the use of secant pile walling. The Contractor for the Pumping Stations - Civil Works Contract No. 2A, proposed the construction of the substructure within a circular sheetpiled cofferdam. Risks associated with such a method of temporary works construction included the difficulty of driving sheet piles into hard strata/rock; the difficulty of maintaining a seal between the interlocks of sheet piles during hard driving leading to drawdown of water in the upper layers and possible settlement of the soft layers; vibration effects arising from hard driving; possible requirements for rock anchors to overcome part of the uplift pressures; and difficulties associated with dewatering at formation level.

Proposals presented by the Contractor were supported by test piling and detailed calculations in respect of sheet pile design and flotation. Concerns about groundwater drawdown leading to

settlement effects on adjacent buildings were also addressed and a system of data loggers and inclines meters were proposed. 4 further boreholes were drilled by the Contractor. An assessment of the potential contaminated soil layers associated with former gas works activities in the area was undertaken and 360m³ of fill material was identified as potentially contaminated with PAH's and cyanides. If removed from site the material could have required special disposal based on Dutch List criteria but the Contractor proposed on site containment of the spoil within a concrete structure external to the Pumping Station Sub-structure but within the cofferdam excavation. Excavation of these layers was monitored by an environmental scientist.

Pumping Stations Construction

Distillery Road Pumping Station was constructed within an 11m x 6.85 x 5m deep cofferdam. It was constructed using 3.6 x 2.4 Magnum Box sides supported by two frames made up of 610 x 305 UB's. The final 1.4m was unsupported as it was in rock.

The cofferdam for Carcur Pump Sump was constructed using Larssen 20 sheet piles supported by a frame made up of 610 x 305 UB's. The piles were driven to 4m below formation level and the cofferdam dimensions were 10.8 x 6.8m x 5.5m deep.

The Quay Pumping Station sump was constructed within a circular sheet piled cofferdam. The Contractor undertook a series of test piling to establish the feasibility of this method. 18 piles were driven in a circle 2m outside the intended line of the proposed cofferdam in Sept. 1998. Following approval of the cofferdam approach an arc shaped piling frame was constructed on site and a steel tubular column was cast into a concrete plinth on the centre point of the cofferdam. The piling frame was able to rotate around this column.

The radius of the cofferdam was 30.354m. The depth of the cofferdam at its deepest point, in the

foul sump, was 11.075m. Larssen LX32 piles, 15 metres long, were used. Grade 50 steel piles were used to counteract the hard driving that was anticipated in the south eastern section of the Cofferdam. A total of 158 piles were required to complete the circle. The cofferdam was designed to be supported by three reinforced concrete circular beams. These beams were cast in situ as the cofferdam was being excavated. Piling was initially carried out using a Vibrating Hammer on a 40 tonne mobile crane. The piling frame was capable of pitching 12 No. piles at each set-up. All piles were pitched and driven to the top of the piling frame in two weeks. A closing pile was welded to tie in the cofferdam. A 6 tonne low frequency vibrating hammer was used to drive the piles through the made ground and sandy silts and gravels down to a depth of 8m approximately. Below this depth a 1.5 tonne BSP Impact Hammer was employed to drive the piles through the stiffer layers of boulder clay and into the mudstones. This impact hammer succeeded in driving three quarters of the piles to the required depth of 13m. A 6 tonne impact hammer was required for the remainder of the piles primarily in the eastern sector of the cofferdam. However a number of the piles in this area could only be driven to a depth which was approximately 1m short of the design depth. The formation of this sector of the cofferdam was only 9.375m deep. For this reason the pile penetration achieved was acceptable.

Excavation commenced six weeks after commencement of piling and the first ring beam 950 x 500mm deep at depth of 4.8m was cast two weeks later. Excavation was carried out by 20 tonne 360° Hydraulic Excavator within the cofferdam double handling spoil to a similar excavator at ground level. Subsequent to the casting of the first Ring Beam excavation continued. A pump sump consisting of 1500mm diam. precast concrete rings was taken down simultaneous with the ongoing excavation operation. The sump was excavated to 1.5m - 2.0m deeper than each dig level. This proved very successful in controlling any ground water and all work was

carried out in a dry environment. To minimise the risk of dewatered groundwater being contaminated from external sources the Contractor modified an outfall culvert constructed at an earlier stage in the works into a temporary oil/water interceptor with internal baffle walls. Discharges from the interceptor were sampled to ensure that groundwater from dewatering operations entering the harbour did not have a significant impact on water quality. The 2nd Ring Beam was 950mm x 750mm deep at a depth of 7.1m and this was cast two weeks after the first beam. The 3rd and final Ring Beam was 950mm x 1000mm deep at depth of 9m and was cast a fortnight later. The floor of the cofferdam was blinded three months after piling commenced (Fig. 6) The base of the structure consisted of a low level incorporating the foul wells and storm wells and a higher level incorporating the inlet section and storage area for contaminated material. The two Base Pours consisted of 244m³ and 140m³ of C40 SRC concrete respectively. Walls were then poured in two lifts, each lift approximately 5m in height, except in the 'contaminated' storage area where walls were poured in one lift. External wall thicknesses were 1.0m to first pour level and 0.8 m for the second lift. Walls pours were completed by Mid June and the final deck pour was carried out in August 1999, eight months after commencement of piling.

Settlement observations on the adjacent buildings were made throughout the construction peri-

FIGURE 6

WEXFORD MAIN DRAINAGE SCHEME

FIGURE 3

The most significant archaeological findings were made in South Main Street and in North Main Street and reflected attempts by earlier residents of the town to reclaim land from the Harbour and also revealed that the building line on South Main Street may have been quite similar to the present day line even as far back as the 12th Century. Evidence of reclamation was revealed over a 64 metre length along South Main Street between Bride St. and Peter Street. Revetments comprising mainly of post and wattle fences, in some cases reinforced on the seaward side with horizontally laid planks, were identified. Reclamation involved the dumping of large deposits of domestic rubbish alternating periodically with layers of flood materials. Overlaying the revetments a substantial paved street surface was recorded for over 30 metres length. The paving was set in a sand bedding. This was dated to the 13th Century. A similar street surface of the same era was identified on reclaimed ground in the North Main Street. Evidence of five street fronting houses dating from the late 12th Century was recorded during excavations for a water main trench in South Main St. (near Bride Street junction). A series of single post and wattle walls were identified roughly in line with the modern property boundaries and parallel with the present Main Street.

Non Negligence Insurance

Under the IEI Conditions of Contract, as in most Contract Forms, the Contractor's liability

for damage to Third Party Property, and his insurance in consequence, is limited to such damage as arises from the Contractor's negligence. The Contract provisions do not require that the non-negligence risk be covered by insurance.

The works proposed for specific streets in the town centre area were of particular concern. The streets are narrow. Oyster Lane is only 3m wide and Monck St. and Charlotte Street are only 4m wide on average (Figure 3). A 900mm dia sewer was proposed to be laid in Monck St. at an average depth to invert of 2.4 to 3.0m over a length of 90 metres.

Consequently deep excavation close to or below the level of footings of the adjoining properties, some of which are three to four stories high, was inevitable. Furthermore the poor ground conditions in areas reclaimed from the foreshore added to the risk.

At the time of Contract Document preparation for Contract No. 1- Pipelines in 1990 non-negligence insurance was not readily available in the insurance market for the type of works proposed, namely the construction of pipelines in a town centre area. The Contract was signed in Sept. 1993, by which time there were indications that insurance companies might be willing to provide non negligence cover for this type of scheme. Consequently, the Contractor was requested to pursue the matter with his insurers. The insurance company was only willing to deal with the request on a Street by Street basis. A quotation was obtained for Lower King Street. The premium advised was £5,000 with a £5,000 excess on each and every claim. Detailed surveys would be required of the properties along the route specific temporary works would have to be provided and all of these measures would have had cost implications for the Contract. This cover was not taken out for Lower King Street.

Non negligence cover was considered to be too expensive to represent value for money when applied to all of the streets which were a cause for concern. The premium cost for non negligence cover for

the town centre area would have been in the region of £250,000 to £500,000, with a high level of excess. This cost would not have included the extensive surveys and temporary works measures stipulated by the insurers and the conditions attached to the cover would have been onerous. In fact if the same conditions as the King St cover applied, they would have been impossible to comply with as a minimum clearance equal to the depth of the trench would have been required between the side of the trench and adjacent buildings.

Due to the nature of the work in the narrow streets of the town, every effort has been taken to minimise the risk arising from the works on adjacent buildings. A photographic survey of the facades of all buildings was carried out immediately prior to commencement of works in a particular street. An engineer from the R.E. staff accompanied the photographer to ensure all cracks and defects were surveyed. Buildings showing signs of deterioration were surveyed and photographed internally also. Dilapidation surveys were undertaken by RE staff on buildings which were in poor condition. Vibration monitoring was carried out where vibrations were likely to be generated either through rock breaking, piling, breaking out of concrete road slabs or movement of heavy plant and machinery. The equipment used was a digital seismograph. In narrow streets with poor ground conditions such as Monck St. backfilling was carried out after each pipe was laid in order to minimise the length of excavation open at any time. Typically only 1^{1/2} pipe lengths (3.75m) of trench were left open in this situation in order to minimise the risk of undermining existing structures. Also pea gravel was vibrated in behind the trench boxes in order to fill any voids created during their installation.

PUMPING STATIONS - CONTRACTS 2A/4A

The collection system as designed entails the construction of three pumping stations to serve the

Bishopswater and Carcur catchments. The existing pumping station at Carcur is to be replaced with a new submersible pumping station capable of delivering up to 350 l/s into the Main Drainage system at the Boat Club. The pumping station at Distillery Road close to Bishopswater Bridge is designed to transfer foul sewage flows from the part of the Bishopswater catchment which has separate foul and surface water sewers to the head of the inlet sewer to the treatment works. This is intended to reduce the foul sewage flows arriving at the main lift pumping station at Trinity Street. The Distillery Road Pumping Station is also a submersible pumping station and is capable of delivering a maximum flow of 411 l/s through three pumps.

Quay Pumping Station Physical Model

The Quay Pumping Station at Trinity Street, South of Wexford Quays, is designed to pump foul sewage and surface water. Combined flows from the town centre area and foul sewage flows from the Carcur catchment, and ultimately from Crosstown

FIGURE 4

Ferrybank on the other side of Wexford Bridge, are directed to this pumping station through the 2.1m diameter Quay Interceptor sewer which eliminates 14 untreated outfalls. Combined flows from the Trinity Street and William Street area of the town also discharge to the Pumping Station via a 900mm dia sewer. The pumping station is designed to pump up to a maximum of 750 l/s forward to the Sewage Treatment Works at Kerlogue via a 700mm dia rising

main laid alongside the railway line. Stormwater inflows will be pumped directly into Wexford Harbour through 4 No. ABS VUP propeller pumps each capable of delivering 2000 l/s against a head of 3.2 metres.

A physical model of the proposed Quay Pumping Station was necessary in order to refine the design of the pumping station sump. In particular, it was required to confirm the flow distribution to the pumps, to ensure that air entraining vortex formation was eliminated and that settlement of solids in dead spots was avoided. A nominated sub contract was included in Contract No. 4A (Pumping Stations Machinery) and after receipt of three tenders the Sub-contract for the physical modelling was awarded to UCD's Centre for Water Resources Research. The model was constructed in the Hydraulics Laboratory of the Department of Civil Engineering, at Earlsfort Terrace.

Model Scale

The model pump sump was constructed to a linear scale of 1:10 resulting in internal sump dimensions of 1070mm by 1600mm and a maximum model sump water depth of 680mm. The design flow for the model was determined by the requirement to reproduce in the model the vortex formation potential of the full scale installation. The flow patterns in sumps are influenced by gravitational, viscous and surface tension forces, which are reflected in the Froude, Reynolds and Weber numbers respectively. It is not possible to scale each of these influences by a single model flow rate. Froudes' Law scaling would result in model velocities equal to 31.6% of the full scale model velocity based on the linear scale of 1:10. Satisfying Reynolds scaling on the other hand would require the model velocity to be 10 times the full scale velocity. Equal velocity has been advocated scaling for pump sump model studies although it is likely to lead to conservative design as it overestimates possible viscosity-related scale effects. UCD's CWRR recommended adopting the equal velocity scaling criterion.

Initial Model Tests

The model sump was constructed in marine plywood with a clear viewing face of polycarbonate sheeting and all internal features of the structure, including pump intakes were reproduced at model scale.

The range of initial tests undertaken covered all of the operational pumping combinations over the full range of water depths. A number of hydraulic deficiencies with the original sump design were apparent after the first series of tests. The flow distribution to the foul pumps was biased towards the pumps nearest the inflow and a dividing wall in the foul sump caused unequal water levels between the two sections of the sump. Turbulence in the sump in storm conditions was considerable and led to significant air entrainment in the storm pump intakes and led to non uniform distribution of flow to each of the pumps.

Model Revisions

The model configuration was revised to ensure more uniform flow distribution to the pumps and to reduce the kinetic energy in the inflow. The inlet from the Quay Interceptor Sewer was revised to incorporate a tapered expansion and an RBI screen. This served to reduce the velocity of inflow and dissipate energy. The benching to the storm sump was modified and simplified. The dividing wall in the foul sump was removed and the profile of the benching in that sump was revised to provide a more uniform distribution of low flows to the foul pumps. These revisions proved very successful but detailed modelling of pump operating levels was necessary to determine a satisfactory regime which ensured sufficient depth of submergence of the pump intakes to avoid air entrainment into the pumps (see Figure 4). Recommendations were made with respect to pump cut in and cut out levels which tallied closely with the pump manufacturer's recommendations.

While air entrained surface vortices were eliminated, the formation of surface vortices between

WEXFORD MAIN DRAINAGE SCHEME

FIGURE 5

the floor of the sump and the intake of the storm pumps was clearly evident under the proposed operating conditions. Sub-surface (forced) vortices are formed by flow and rotation and their formation beneath propeller pump intakes has been studied extensively by ABS Pumps, the pump suppliers, who recommended that the wall behind the pump intakes be profiled and that the floor beneath the pumps be roughened. These revisions were incorporated in the model and the problem of sub surface vortices were eliminated. With the revised layout of the sump the flow distribution to each of the storm pumps was reasonably uniform and dead zones appeared to be minimum. This final layout formed the basis for the Civil Works design which is shown at Figure 5.

Pumping Stations - Civil Works Design.

An extensive site investigation was undertaken in respect of the Quay Pumping Station with boreholes

drilled by IGSL in 1986 and again in 1996/97. The Quay Pumping Station is located on a site between Trinity Street and the Railway line at the Southern end of Wexford Quay. The general ground level on the site is 4.7m to 5m OD. The tidal variation in Wexford Harbour is 3.13m OD MHWST down to 1.63m OD MLWST although tides as high as 4.4m OD were recorded during the course of the Pipelines Contract No. 1. (January 1996). The site of the pumping station had been reclaimed from the sea (probably after 1840) and was formerly the Wexford South Station on the Dublin Rosslare railway line. Also, a Gasworks was located on or close to the site in the past.

The stratification of the site is confused, partly due to the reclamation of the land, but also due to the weathered nature of the bedrock which sometimes cannot be distinguished from a very stiff cohesive fill. The upper strata about +0.5m OD to -1.5m OD

comprises fill and soft/loose organic silts and loose sands. These overlie medium dense/dense gravels and firm to very stiff sandy silt and boulder clays to about - 3.5m OD. The soil/rocks below that level comprise possible very stiff cohesive tills, dense gravels or weathered rock. The sump dimensions are 10.7m x 16m internally with a depth to formation of 11 metres. Pumping tests were undertaken by IGSL to establish groundwater drawdown associated with potential dewatering. The geotechnical considerations relevant to the proposed development included method of construction of the pumping station, the effects of ground water lowering and of the construction on the buildings and adjacent railway together with uplift considerations both during construction and on the finished structure. The scheme went to tender based on a monolithic watertight reinforced concrete structure including base slab walls and suspended slab at ground level within a perimeter secant piled wall. The secant piled wall was intended to contribute additional weight towards the resistance of buoyancy uplift on the substructure.

The Contractor was entitled to offer alternatives to the use of secant pile walling. The Contractor for the Pumping Stations - Civil Works Contract No. 2A, proposed the construction of the substructure within a circular sheetpiled cofferdam. Risks associated with such a method of temporary works construction included the difficulty of driving sheet piles into hard strata/rock; the difficulty of maintaining a seal between the interlocks of sheet piles during hard driving leading to drawdown of water in the upper layers and possible settlement of the soft layers; vibration effects arising from hard driving; possible requirements for rock anchors to overcome part of the uplift pressures; and difficulties associated with dewatering at formation level.

Proposals presented by the Contractor were supported by test piling and detailed calculations in respect of sheet pile design and flotation. Concerns about groundwater drawdown leading to

settlement effects on adjacent buildings were also addressed and a system of data loggers and inclines meters were proposed. 4 further boreholes were drilled by the Contractor. An assessment of the potential contaminated soil layers associated with former gas works activities in the area was undertaken and 360m³ of fill material was identified as potentially contaminated with PAH's and cyanides. If removed from site the material could have required special disposal based on Dutch List criteria but the Contractor proposed on site containment of the spoil within a concrete structure external to the Pumping Station Sub-structure but within the cofferdam excavation. Excavation of these layers was monitored by an environmental scientist.

Pumping Stations Construction

Distillery Road Pumping Station was constructed within an 11m x 6.85 x 5m deep cofferdam. It was constructed using 3.6 x 2.4 Magnum Box sides supported by two frames made up of 610 x 305 UB's. The final 1.4m was unsupported as it was in rock.

The cofferdam for Carcur Pump Sump was constructed using Larssen 20 sheet piles supported by a frame made up of 610 x 305 UB's. The piles were driven to 4m below formation level and the cofferdam dimensions were 10.8 x 6.8m x 5.5m deep.

The Quay Pumping Station sump was constructed within a circular sheet piled cofferdam. The Contractor undertook a series of test piling to establish the feasibility of this method. 18 piles were driven in a circle 2m outside the intended line of the proposed cofferdam in Sept. 1998. Following approval of the cofferdam approach an arc shaped piling frame was constructed on site and a steel tubular column was cast into a concrete plinth on the centre point of the cofferdam. The piling frame was able to rotate around this column. The radius of the cofferdam was 30.354m. The depth of the cofferdam at its deepest point, in the

foul sump, was 11.075m. Larssen LX32 piles, 15 metres long, were used. Grade 50 steel piles were used to counteract the hard driving that was anticipated in the south eastern section of the Cofferdam. A total of 158 piles were required to complete the circle. The cofferdam was designed to be supported by three reinforced concrete circular beams. These beams were cast in situ as the cofferdam was being excavated. Piling was initially carried out using a Vibrating Hammer on a 40 tonne mobile crane. The piling frame was capable of pitching 12 No. piles at each set-up. All piles were pitched and driven to the top of the piling frame in two weeks. A closing pile was welded to tie in the cofferdam. A 6 tonne low frequency vibrating hammer was used to drive the piles through the made ground and sandy silts and gravels down to a depth of 8m approximately. Below this depth a 1.5 tonne BSP Impact Hammer was employed to drive the piles through the stiffer layers of boulder clay and into the mudstones. This impact hammer succeeded in driving three quarters of the piles to the required depth of 13m. A 6 tonne impact hammer was required for the remainder of the piles primarily in the eastern sector of the cofferdam. However a number of the piles in this area could only be driven to a depth which was approximately 1m short of the design depth. The formation of this sector of the cofferdam was only 9.375m deep. For this reason the pile penetration achieved was acceptable.

Excavation commenced six weeks after commencement of piling and the first ring beam 950 x 500mm deep at depth of 4.8m was cast two weeks later. Excavation was carried out by 20 tonne 360° Hydraulic Excavator within the cofferdam double handling spoil to a similar excavator at ground level. Subsequent to the casting of the first Ring Beam excavation continued. A pump sump consisting of 1500mm diam. precast concrete rings was taken down simultaneous with the ongoing excavation operation. The sump was excavated to 1.5m - 2.0m deeper than each dig level. This proved very successful in controlling any ground water and all work was

carried out in a dry environment. To minimise the risk of dewatered groundwater being contaminated from external sources the Contractor modified an outfall culvert constructed at an earlier stage in the works into a temporary oil/water interceptor with internal baffle walls. Discharges from the interceptor were sampled to ensure that groundwater from dewatering operations entering the harbour did not have a significant impact on water quality. The 2nd Ring Beam was 950mm x 750mm deep at a depth of 7.1m and this was cast two weeks after the first beam. The 3rd and final Ring Beam was 950mm x 1000mm deep at depth of 9m and was cast a fortnight later. The floor of the cofferdam was blinded three months after piling commenced (Fig. 6) The base of the structure consisted of a low level incorporating the foul wells and storm wells and a higher lever incorporating the inlet section and storage area for contaminated material. The two Base Pours consisted of 244m³ and 140m³ of C40 SRC concrete respectively. Walls were then poured in two lifts, each lift approximately 5m in height, except in the 'contaminated' storage area where walls were poured in one lift. External wall thicknesses were 1.0m to first pour level and 0.8 m for the second lift. Walls pours were completed by Mid June and the final deck pour was carried out in August 1999, eight months after commencement of piling.

Settlement observations on the adjacent buildings were made throughout the construction peri-

FIGURE 6

WEXFORD MAIN DRAINAGE SCHEME

od. Dataloggers were installed at seven points on an 35 metre long inclinometer beam along the wall of the adjacent warehouse and readings were taken at 1/2 hour intervals throughout the period the excavation was open. No significant settlement was observed in any adjacent building. The datalogger did however record a very small variation (of the order of 0.5mm) in levels between incoming and outgoing tides. A prior dilapidation survey had identified existing cracks in the buildings and these were marked with telltales. These did not show any significant deterioration through the construction period.

QUAY INTERCEPTOR SEWER

Background

The centre of Wexford Town as described earlier is low lying and prone to flooding due to tidal back-up. The design of the main drainage scheme provides for the interception of all flows discharged through the quay front in a 2100mm diameter interceptor sewer. This sewer discharges to a main lift pumping station where all foul sewage flows and first flush storm flows will be pumped forward for treatment. Excess storm water will be lifted above tide level for discharge locally at the pump station.

A number of options were considered for the route of the interceptor sewer along the quayfront. These included:

- i). Construction in open cut and tunnel along the existing roadway,
- ii). Construction on piles outside the quay wall which would have involved the removal and replacement of the existing timber wharf serving the commenced fishing industry,
- iii). Construction within an embankment to be reclaimed in front of the existing quays.

Following detailed consideration by the various authorities, Option (iii) was adopted subject to its feasibility of construction. While more expensive in terms of con-

struction costs, it provided for much reduced impacts on the commercial town centre environment and was in keeping with the local authorities, future development plans for the quayfront area.

Modelling and Surveys

The feasibility of constructing an embankment along the quay front was assessed in terms of:

- * it's stability and effect on the existing quay wall and railway line, running along the edge of the quay.
- * it's effect on the flow regime in the harbour estuary,
- * its impact on the commercial and leisure interests using the existing quays, and
- * the extent and width required to facilitate the safe construction of the interceptor sewer.

Sub-soil Investigations

Two sub-soil investigations were carried out in the harbour for this embankment, the first in 1983 which confirmed the feasibility of constructing the embankment and the second in 1986 prior to the detailed design stage. The findings of these two investigations are reported on separately and have been simplified in the stratifications shown at Table 1 for the purposes of this paper.

In addition to the two marine based surveys, an extensive ground investigation was carried out in the town in 1991 for the pipeline contract. The boreholes along the

quays confirmed a similar pattern of made ground, upper and lower level alluvium and the occurrence of an intermediate peat layer at some locations at about -3m OD to -6m OD (Poolbeg Datum). The alluvium could be described as very soft silts, generally sandy with sand and gravel layers or pockets and with some peat. The upper layers are mostly very variable organic silts/clays of high water content with peat layers while the lower layers were generally less compressible silty sands/sandy silts and medium dense gravels of consistent strength. The underlying glacial deposits comprise medium dense and dense gravels and firm to stiff, sometimes very stiff, sandy gravelly clay (boulder clay). Rock encountered at depth comprised moderately strong to strong sand stones and strong quartzites with bands of shaley or slaty rocks.

A separate investigation was carried out along the line of the existing quay wall. This investigation found that the material to the rear of the face of the wall was of poor quality and that, in places, the possibility was that the wall was founded on soft soils. Insofar as the bottom of the wall could be identified, it appeared to be founded at levels varying from -3m OD to -6.0m OD (Poolbeg Datum).

Based on the various investigations carried out it was decided to remove the upper alluvial and peat layers and to found the embankment on the lower alluvial and glacial till deposits.

Hydraulic Model Analysis

Hydraulic model tests were carried out at the Hydraulics and Maritime Research Centre (HMRC) of

Stratum	Description	Level of Bottom
1. Made Ground	Sand, gravel, cobbles, bits of pottery etc. (encountered in land boreholes only)	+2 to -1m O.D.
2. Upper alluvials	Generally organic Clay in BH 1,2 and 3, a sandy silt in 4 & 5 and sandy gravel in BH 6	-2.76 to -10.2
3. Peats	Encountered in BH 832, 836 and 838	-3.96 to -5.16
4. Lower alluvials	sands, silty sands and sandy silts	varies to -19.7
5. Gravels or possible glacial till	generally dense angular or subangular gravel with cobbles, sometimes in a clay matrix	not fully penetrated
6. Possible rockhead	not clearly identifiable	not fully penetrated

TABLE 1

WEXFORD MAIN DRAINAGE SCHEME

University College Cork to assess the impacts of the proposed embankment on the flow regime in the harbour and to optimise the shape and configuration of the embankment structure. The initial hydraulic model study was carried out in 1986 and comprised the prediction of design loading conditions, numeral modelling and two and three dimensional physical model tests. The additional model testing carried out in 1997 was necessary due to revised facade proposals for various sections of the quay front. Three dimensional 1:100 (1986) and 1:80 (1997) (see figure 7) scale models of the existing harbour section in front of the quays and of the proposed embankment were constructed to determine wave penetration and flow velocities within the harbour and how the proposed embankment structure influenced wave propagation and currents. Two dimensional, 1:22

scale models of a typical section of the embankment (1986 and 1996) were used to assess the stability of the rock armour units and to ascertain likelihood of run-up and overtopping in storm conditions.

The environmental conditions relevant to the Wexford quays were determined by HMRC by carrying out an analysis of wind, wave, tidal heights, currents and storm surge condition. A detailed refraction analysis was also carried out to determine wave propagation into the quays. Table 2 summarises the predicted wave heights, tide levels and surges.

The above return periods are for the E.N.E. direction only. In the analysis it was assumed that surges from other directions would not be as large due to limited fetch length and due to the shallow water levels at the entrance to the harbour.

As part of this study, measurements were also made of tidal currents and a detailed bathymetric survey was made of the harbour bed in order to construct the model which was then calibrated against field measurements.

The test variables included the angle of wave approach, wave period and breakwater configuration (location and length). These tests along with the flow tests were instrumental in determining the configuration and design of the structure for the 1:100 year design period.

Design

A width of 15m was considered to be the minimum required for the embankment to construct the interceptor sewer within a sheet piled cofferdam and this width was adopted south of the Crescent. Increased widths, up to 35m, were required for the commercial fishing and amenity uses between the Crescent and Wexford Bridge. The overall length required was approximately 850 metres.

Arising from the sub-soil investigations, the decision to dredge and remove the upper alluvial and peat layers, resulted in formation levels

generally varying between -6.0m and -9.0m OD (Poolbeg Datum) between the Crescent and the Bridge (600 metres long approx.) and levels of approximately -3.0 m to -6.0m OD for the remaining 250m length south of the Crescent. This gave a maximum height of embankment of about 13.5m to 14m.

The embankment design comprised an outer rockfill core protected by primary armour, secondary armour and filter layer. The option was allowed for the use of either rockfill or hydraulic fill as the infill material between the existing quay wall and the main core. A suitable source for hydraulic fill was identified in the area of Holden's Bed off Rosslare. The area had been used previously by Iarnrod Eireann as part of its beach nourishment works at Rosslare. The embankment was designed to have a minimum slope factor of safety of 1.25 against slope failure for the construction stage of the works increasing thereafter as the under layers consolidated. In order to achieve this factor of safety on the section around the Crescent and northwards towards the bridge, provision was made in the contract for a two stage filling operation with the first stage filling placed to a max. height of 2.5m OD until such time as the lower alluvial underlying layers had consolidated which was to be verified by piezometric and settlement block monitoring. A shear key was provided along the full length of the toe of the embankment to improve its stability.

The size of rock armour units were determined using Hudson's formula:

$$W = \frac{S_r \times \rho \times H_s^3}{K_d \times (S_r - 1)^3 \times \cot a}$$

where:

W = Weight of an individual armour units in Kgs.

ρ = unit wt of water

Hs = Significant Wave Height (m) at the structure

Sr = Specific gravity of the armour unit

a = Angle of structure slope

Kd = Stability co-efficient for the type of armour used.

FIGURE 7

WEXFORD MAIN DRAINAGE SCHEME

Return Period (Years)	Sign. Wave Height (m)
1	0.59
10	0.87
25	1
50	1.10
100	1.20

Predicted Wave Heights

Tide Type	Levels (m.O.D.)
MHWS	3.13
MHWN	2.83
MLWN	1.93
MLWS	1.63
HAT	3.38

Tide Levels (Poolbeg Datum)

Return Period (Years)	Surge (m)	Surge and Tide (m.O.D.)
1	0.36	3.49
10	0.67	3.80
25	0.92	4.05
50	1.04	4.17
100	1.20	4.33

Surge levels at Quay

TABLE 2

Type	Description (Uniform Grading)
Primary Armour Cover to be 2 layers Min thickness 1.28m	Max unit weight not greater than 620kg. Min unit weight not less than 370 kg 75% of units between 500kg and 620 kg Max unit size 705mm Sp.G 2.7 Min unit size 595mm Sp.G 2.7
Secondary Armour Cover to be 2 layers Min thickness 0.58m	Max unit weight not greater than 62kg. Min unit weight not less than 37 kg 75% of units between 50kg and 62 kg Max unit size 325mm Sp.G 2.7 Min unit size 275mm Sp.G 2.7
Filter Layer No. 1 Min Thickness 0.5m	(i) 70mm D_{85} <math>< 230\text{mm}</math> (Approx values) (ii) 60mm D_{15} <math>< 90\text{mm}</math>

Design Grading for Armour Materials

TABLE 3

The protection layers were designed in accordance with the methods outlined in the "Shore Protection Manual" (US Army Corps of Engineers) and other publications including those of the Danish Hydraulic Institute. To prevent smaller rocks in the underlayer being pulled through the outer layers by wave action, the criterion used for filter design was:

$$D15 (\text{cover}) < 5 D85 (\text{under})$$

where $D85$ (under) is the diameter exceeded by the coarsest 15% of the underlayer and $D15$ (cover) is the diameter exceeded by the coarsest 85% of the layer immediately above the under layer.

Based on the hydraulic model tests and on the above publications the rock material grading given in Table 3 was adopted for the armour layers.

A separate filter layer was designed between the inner face of the rock core and the general fill material between the core and the quay wall. However as the entire embankment was eventually constructed using the same material

ORIGINAL BERTHING DESIGN SYSTEM AND EMBANKMENT

FIGURE 8

this filter was not needed.

The interceptor sewer within the embankment was designed as a flexible concrete pipe system supported on a reinforced concrete cradle. Calculations of the primary settlement of the embankment were estimated at 250 - 300mm and that this would occur within the first six to twelve months after filling. The secondary settlement was estimated at 25mm to 50mm. Therefore provision was made in the contract to defer the construction of the sewer until twelve months after the completion of any section of the embankment. The construction of the interceptor sewer also necessitated the removal or cutting off to below formation level of the old timber wharf south of and in the area of the Crescent.

During the time of the preparation of the contract documents, the usable length of the timber wharf was about 150 - 200 metres depending on tidal conditions. Provision was made for 180 metres of replacement berthing comprising in-situ reinforced concrete deckslab on precast prestressed bridge beams on steel piles filled with reinforced concrete. (see Figure 8) However, an alternative design was later adopted as described below and the length of berthing was increased to 350 metres. Temporary berthing facilities were to be provided for the commercial shellfish fishermen to facilitate the construction of the embankment and of the sewer. This was provided by a 100m long sheet piled wall and 50m of floating pontoons.

FIGURE 9

The model testing by HMRC also confirmed that some sedimentation build up would occur inside the breakwater and immediately downstream of it. In order to limit this build up five scour culverts were incorporated at low level in the breakwater arm to achieve some degree of flushing action in this area. Four 1800mm diameter HDPE pipe lengths and one length of 4500mm x 2150mm precast concrete culvert were used for the scour culverts. Previous recorded maximum tide levels at Wexford were 4.0m OD Poolbeg Datum. The existing quay ranged in level from 4.1m to 4.7m OD. Given the expected increase in sea levels in conjunction with the hydraulic model tests, the design level adopted for the embankment was 4.5 m.O.D. (Poolbeg) for the area north of the Crescent protected by the Breakwater arm with a wave wall to 5.5 m.O.D. along the breakwater and south embankment.

Subsequent revisions were made during construction as a result of increased tide level observations in storm conditions in 1996 and due to additional hydraulic modelling (Figure 9) carried out in 1996/97.

WEXFORD MAIN DRAINAGE SCHEME

The embankment edge level was raised to 4.7 m.O.D., the height of wave wall was retained at 5.5 m.O.D., on the south embankment but was reduced to 5.0 m.O.D. along the breakwater arm. A 2 m wide berm was recommended on the top armour outside the wave wall (approx. level 4.7m OD) and a recurve was provided in the outer face of the wave wall.

CONSTRUCTION

At the commencement of the contract two lines of boreholes were taken from floating craft along the full length of the embankment at 50m centres to verify the information obtained from previous investigations. A full bathymetric survey of the quayfront was also carried out to establish base bed levels.

Construction works commenced at the South end of the embankment since this area of the quays was not in use, the existing timber wharf was in a dilapidated state of decay and disrepair and this section of the embankment required least depths of dredging and least quantities of filling.

The main components of the old berthing wharf comprised 300 x 300mm pitch pipe or greenheart timber sections of varying pile lengths, mostly between 10m to 15m. Rather than cut these below formation level, the Contractor elected to remove them by pulling, having first loosened them with a vibrating hammer. This work took place in 5m to 10m sections along the quay wall simultaneously with the dredging and filling operations in order to safeguard the stability of the existing quay wall and of the railway line.

The Contractor's proposal for disposal of dredged material was based on the bunding and reclamation of an area of the foreshore using the dredged material immediately downstream of Wexford Bridge, behind the North Training Wall. Pending receipt of the necessary approvals for this site from the Department of the Marine and Natural Resources, disposal of the dredge material took place to land

and to landfill. Dredging was carried out using a crane and grab mounted on a pontoon and the dredged material was loaded onto trucks for land disposal and later to dump barges which were transported by tug to the North Training Wall disposal site for unloading into the bunded area. In the mid and latter stages of the contract, the majority of the dredging work was carried out by a long reach excavator. The total quantity of material dredged from the quay front area was about 135,000m³.

The Contractor's tender for the works was based on the use of rockfill rather than hydraulic fill. The option of transporting fill to the site by barge along the Slaney was examined at the start of the contract but this was abandoned due to the unavailability of a suitable or approved source close to the river. The restricted clearance through the bridge at Ferrycarrig also mitigated against this option. The total quantity of imported fill amounted to approximately 300,000m³ (excluding the armour protection layers) resulting in a reclaimed area of 2.4hA..

During the initial filling operations from the quay wall outwards it was found that the amount of fine sediment escaping from the fill was quite limited and the water quality requirements stipulated in the foreshore licence for this work were satisfied. The filling operations were therefore allowed to proceed from the exist-

FIGURE 10

FIGURE 11

ing quay wall outwards without the need firstly to construct the outer rock core as had been intended in order to limit the egress of fine material to the harbour. (see Figure 10) The full width section of embankment south of the Crescent was completed in this manner followed by the filter layer and armour layers (secondary and primary) on the outer face.

Construction of the interceptor sewer commenced approximately twelve months after the filling was completed and followed the filling operations commencing at the southern end. The construction of the sewer was carried out within a series of 50 metre (approx.) lengths of sheet piled cofferdam taken down to cut-off levels of -6m OD to -11m OD approx. Ground level at the top of the cofferdam was maintained at about 3.5m OD and the invert level of the sewer ranged from - 3.0 m OD to 0.0 mOD along the quayfront. The excavation and dewatering operations inside the cofferdams were well controlled throughout and ground water levels were monitored on the far side of the quays to check the drawdown. The formation was levelled and overlaid with a 200mm thick concrete blinding layer to provide a solid working platform. The pipes were placed on support blocks and the concrete cradle was cast, all in dry working conditions. (see Figure 11) Having backfilled the trench the cofferdam was pulled and re-dried for another section ahead.

A rock outcrop approximately 40m long was encountered outside Custom House Quay. This required

WEXFORD MAIN DRAINAGE SCHEME

od. Dataloggers were installed at seven points on a 35 metre long inclinometer beam along the wall of the adjacent warehouse and readings were taken at 1/2 hour intervals throughout the period the excavation was open. No significant settlement was observed in any adjacent building. The datalogger did however record a very small variation (of the order of 0.5mm) in levels between incoming and outgoing tides. A prior dilapidation survey had identified existing cracks in the buildings and these were marked with telltales. These did not show any significant deterioration through the construction period.

QUAY INTERCEPTOR SEWER

Background

The centre of Wexford Town as described earlier is low lying and prone to flooding due to tidal back-up. The design of the main drainage scheme provides for the interception of all flows discharged through the quay front in a 2100mm diameter interceptor sewer. This sewer discharges to a main lift pumping station where all foul sewage flows and first flush storm flows will be pumped forward for treatment. Excess storm water will be lifted above tide level for discharge locally at the pump station.

A number of options were considered for the route of the interceptor sewer along the quayfront. These included:

- i). Construction in open cut and tunnel along the existing roadway,
- ii). Construction on piles outside the quay wall which would have involved the removal and replacement of the existing timber wharf serving the commenced fishing industry,
- iii). Construction within an embankment to be reclaimed in front of the existing quays.

Following detailed consideration by the various authorities, Option (iii) was adopted subject to its feasibility of construction. While more expensive in terms of con-

struction costs, it provided for much reduced impacts on the commercial town centre environment and was in keeping with the local authorities, future development plans for the quayfront area.

Modelling and Surveys

The feasibility of constructing an embankment along the quay front was assessed in terms of:

- * its stability and effect on the existing quay wall and railway line, running along the edge of the quay.
- * its effect on the flow regime in the harbour estuary,
- * its impact on the commercial and leisure interests using the existing quays, and
- * the extent and width required to facilitate the safe construction of the interceptor sewer.

Sub-soil Investigations

Two sub-soil investigations were carried out in the harbour for this embankment, the first in 1983 which confirmed the feasibility of constructing the embankment and the second in 1986 prior to the detailed design stage. The findings of these two investigations are reported on separately and have been simplified in the stratifications shown at Table 1 for the purposes of this paper.

In addition to the two marine based surveys, an extensive ground investigation was carried out in the town in 1991 for the pipeline contract. The boreholes along the

quays confirmed a similar pattern of made ground, upper and lower level alluvium and the occurrence of an intermediate peat layer at some locations at about -3m OD to -6m OD (Poolbeg Datum). The alluvium could be described as very soft silts, generally sandy with sand and gravel layers or pockets and with some peat. The upper layers are mostly very variable organic silts/clays of high water content with peat layers while the lower layers were generally less compressible silty sands/sandy silts and medium dense gravels of consistent strength. The underlying glacial deposits comprise medium dense and dense gravels and firm to stiff, sometimes very stiff, sandy gravelly clay (boulder clay). Rock encountered at depth comprised moderately strong to strong sand stones and strong quartzites with bands of shaley or slaty rocks.

A separate investigation was carried out along the line of the existing quay wall. This investigation found that the material to the rear of the face of the wall was of poor quality and that, in places, the possibility was that the wall was founded on soft soils. Insofar as the bottom of the wall could be identified, it appeared to be founded at levels varying from -3m OD to -6.0m OD (Poolbeg Datum).

Based on the various investigations carried out it was decided to remove the upper alluvial and peat layers and to found the embankment on the lower alluvial and glacial till deposits.

Hydraulic Model Analysis

Hydraulic model tests were carried out at the Hydraulics and Maritime Research Centre (HMRC) of

Stratum	Description	Level of Bottom
1. Made Ground	Sand, gravel, cobbles, bits of pottery etc. (encountered in land boreholes only)	+2 to -1m O.D.
2. Upper alluvials	Generally organic Clay in BH 1,2 and 3, a sandy silt in 4 & 5 and sandy gravel in BH 6	-2.76 to -10.2
3. Peats	Encountered in BH 832, 836 and 838	-3.96 to -5.16
4. Lower alluvials	sands, silty sands and sandy silts	varies to -19.7
5. Gravels or possible glacial till	generally dense angular or subangular gravel with cobbles, sometimes in a clay matrix	not fully penetrated
6. Possible rockhead	not clearly identifiable	not fully penetrated

TABLE 1

WEXFORD MAIN DRAINAGE SCHEME

University College Cork to assess the impacts of the proposed embankment on the flow regime in the harbour and to optimise the shape and configuration of the embankment structure. The initial hydraulic model study was carried out in 1986 and comprised the prediction of design loading conditions, numeral modelling and two and three dimensional physical model tests. The additional model testing carried out in 1997 was necessary due to revised facade proposals for various sections of the quay front. Three dimensional 1:100 (1986) and 1:80 (1997) (see figure 7) scale models of the existing harbour section in front of the quays and of the proposed embankment were constructed to determine wave penetration and flow velocities within the harbour and how the proposed embankment structure influenced wave propagation and currents. Two dimensional, 1:22

scale models of a typical section of the embankment (1986 and 1996) were used to assess the stability of the rock armour units and to ascertain likelihood of run-up and overtopping in storm conditions.

The environmental conditions relevant to the Wexford quays were determined by HMRC by carrying out an analysis of wind, wave, tidal heights, currents and storm surge condition. A detailed refraction analysis was also carried out to determine wave propagation into the quays. Table 2 summarises the predicted wave heights, tide levels and surges.

The above return periods are for the E.N.E. direction only. In the analysis it was assumed that surges from other directions would not be as large due to limited fetch length and due to the shallow water levels at the entrance to the harbour.

As part of this study, measurements were also made of tidal currents and a detailed bathymetric survey was made of the harbour bed in order to construct the model which was then calibrated against field measurements.

The test variables included the angle of wave approach, wave period and breakwater configuration (location and length). These tests along with the flow tests were instrumental in determining the configuration and design of the structure for the 1:100 year design period.

Design

A width of 15m was considered to be the minimum required for the embankment to construct the interceptor sewer within a sheet piled cofferdam and this width was adopted south of the Crescent. Increased widths, up to 35m, were required for the commercial fishing and amenity uses between the Crescent and Wexford Bridge. The overall length required was approximately 850 metres.

Arising from the sub-soil investigations, the decision to dredge and remove the upper alluvial and peat layers, resulted in formation levels

generally varying between -6.0m and -9.0m OD (Poolbeg Datum) between the Crescent and the Bridge (600 metres long approx.) and levels of approximately -3.0m to -6.0m OD for the remaining 250m length south of the Crescent. This gave a maximum height of embankment of about 13.5m to 14m.

The embankment design comprised an outer rockfill core protected by primary armour, secondary armour and filter layer. The option was allowed for the use of either rockfill or hydraulic fill as the infill material between the existing quay wall and the main core. A suitable source for hydraulic fill was identified in the area of Holden's Bed off Rosslare. The area had been used previously by Iarnrod Eireann as part of its beach nourishment works at Rosslare. The embankment was designed to have a minimum factor of safety of 1.25 against slope failure for the construction stage of the works increasing thereafter as the under layers consolidated. In order to achieve this factor of safety on the section around the Crescent and northwards towards the bridge, provision was made in the contract for a two stage filling operation with the first stage filling placed to a max. height of 2.5m OD until such time as the lower alluvial underlying layers had consolidated which was to be verified by piezometric and settlement block monitoring. A shear key was provided along the full length of the toe of the embankment to improve its stability.

The size of rock armour units were determined using Hudson's formula:

$$W = \frac{S_r \times \rho \times H_s^3}{K_d \times (S_r - 1)^3 \times \cot a}$$

where:

W = Weight of an individual armour units in Kgs.

ρ = unit wt of water

H_s = Significant Wave Height (m) at the structure

S_r = Specific gravity of the armour unit

a = Angle of structure slope

K_d = Stability co-efficient for the type of armour used.

FIGURE 7

WEXFORD MAIN DRAINAGE SCHEME

Finished Deck

The deck is finished in hard paving in keeping with the general requirements for a quayfront area. Concrete paviors have been used on the section north of the Crescent with bands of limestone setts in areas other than the boardwalk. The granite cope stone of the old quay front has been raised and re-aligned to delineate the boundary of the new embankment and the former quay. A 10m wide, 250 m long concrete deck has been provided as a working dock for the commercial fishermen at the quay front.

Dredge Disposal Area

The area used for the disposal of the dredged soft material from the quayfront immediately behind the North Training Wall had been used in the past as a disposal site during the construction of Wexford Bridge and for dredge disposal from routine maintenance of the harbour. This resulted in the creation of a man made mudflat in this area. No objections were raised during the foreshore application for this area and a lease was granted for the reclamation of a 5ha site using the dredged material.

However nearing completion of the disposal /reclamation works, representations were made to the European Commission that since the Harbour outside the Training Walls was proposed to be designated as a Natural Heritage Area (NHA) it should be protected under the Habitats Directive (92/43 EEC). It was argued that compensatory measures should be provided to replace the area of mudflat lost due to the reclamation works. Following consultations with Duchas and the Irish Wildbird Conservancy, agreement was reached to provide a replacement area of mudflat adjacent to the reclamation area. Again HMRC were engaged due to their knowledge of the harbour to assess the potential for natural mudflat regeneration in the area. They found that this was not likely to occur since, on the contrary, the Ferrybank coastline was very prone to erosion. The replacement area of mudflat is proposed

to be contained within a fish tail groyne which will serve the dual function of retaining the mudflat and of protecting a section of the coastline from erosion. An application is currently with the Department of the Marine and Natural Resources for this proposal.

PRINCIPAL QUANTITIES

Pipelines:

Sewers:	25,000m
Watermains:	10,000m
Ducting:	15,000m

Quay Pumping Stations:

Cofferdam:	30.35m diam. 11m deep
Excavation:	6730m ³
Concrete:	2170m ³

Quay Extension/ Interceptor Sewer

1800mm:	240m
2100mm:	630m
Dredge Material:	135,000m ³
Rockfill:	300,000m ³
Armour Stone:	36,500m ³
Concrete:	7,500m ³
Steel Reinforcement:	600T
Steel Plate:	370T
Fenders (300sq.)	800m
Scour Culverts:	(4.5m x 2.15m)
Reclamation Area:	24,000m ²
Timber Decking:	4220m ²
Flexible paving:	6030m ²
Block Paviors:	8875m ²
Concrete Deck:	2500m ²
Concrete Promenade:	2375m ²

CONSTRUCTION COSTS:

Pipelines:	£12.5M
Pumping Stations:	£3.8M
Quay Extension/ Interceptor Sewer:	£16.0M

CONTRACTORS

Pipeline Contracts:

Messrs Pat Mulcair
Messrs Mathew Wallace Ltd.

Pumping Stations:

Civil
Messrs Pat Mulcair

Mechanical & Engineering
Messrs USF Bowen Water
Technology Ltd..

Quay Extension/Int. Sewer:

Messrs Irishenco
Messrs Pat Mulcair

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.

The authors wish to thank all those who have co-operated with and assisted in the works described in this paper. In particular we wish to acknowledge Mr. S. Dooley, County Manager, Mr. J. Hutchinson, Assistant County Manager, Mr P. Callery County Engineer, Mr. T. Fahey, Borough Engineer and Mr. D. Curtin, Town Clerk for their support throughout the project and for their permission to present this paper. Our thanks are also due to the various staff members in both the DOELG and Wexford Harbour Commissioners for their guidance and assistance to us the various contractors involved in the construction of the works.

We would like to thank Mr. R.F. Coote, Senior RE and Messrs M. Dee and J. Crowley, Deputy RE and their entire staff for their work on the project and for their help in the preparation of this paper. To our own office colleagues and to Mr. T. Lewis and Dr. J. Murphy of HMRC and to Mr. P. J. Purcell of CWRR., we also express our thanks.

Var.
27° 15'
W.

Soundings at Low Water
in feet

High Water Rosslare Pt 6h 30m
Springs rise 5th Neaps 3ft

Sea Mile

S o u t h B a y

Memo to Eddie Fitzgerald
From Eric Farrell

Re: Figures of paper/presentation

Eddie,

It would be great if you could get the following figures for the presentation which could also be included in the paper:-

Figure 1 - Slide 1 Extent of the Main Drainage Contract on a map of Wexford.
Should show Quay extension, Pumping Station, NTW and original site of STW

Figure 2 and Slide 2 – Map of Wexford with contours and showing rivers.

Figure 6, Slide 7 – Photo of Quay Wall, preferably with train running across before the land was reclaimed. I propose to use this to illustrate the problem of the quay wall.

Figure 6 Alluvial deposits – my estimate of zone of alluvial.

Figure 7 – Slide 10 Locations of section behind quay and in front of quay

Figure 8 Slide 11 Ground profile behind Quay illustrating soft and peat. (the section that I dropped in yesterday).

Slide 16 ~~repeat~~ of (Figure 8, Slide 10) as intro. to discussion on Quay Extension

Figures 8, 10, 11 (Slide 17, 18 & 19) – section through the quay showing, if possible, the shear key proposal.

Figure 12 – slide 20, ground profile in front of quay, showing soft silt extending to – 17mOD.

Figure 14 slide 23 – Photo of NTW

Figure 16 – slide 25 ~~Repeat~~ of Slide 1, to be used to locate old STW site.

Figure 17, slide 27 – rock outcrops.- I will leave this one to your section of the presentation.

Eddie, I think that you will have most of these handy. The presentation is at 6.30 on Monday in Dublin. I am concerned that few will attend as it has been given very little publicity.

Regards

Eric

reference to the
 as destroyed by the
 in June 1798.

- 1 The Custom House.
- 2 Cap. Sal. Bond.
- 3 Mr. Abraham Broughton.
- 4 Mr. John Callaghan.
- 5 The Rev. Mr. Miller.
- 6 Mr. Edwards.
- 7 Knight's House.
- 8 Market House.
- 9 The Jail.
- 10 Mr. Hutchins House.
- 11 The Prison Ship.
- 12 Lord Kingsboroughs Lodgings.
- 13 Brig. Harveys Lodgings.
- 14 Mr. ... House.

A Plan of the Town of
WEXFORD
On a Scale of 200 Feet to an Inch
By Peter Fennell
Master in the Navy
 1800.

2. FENNELLS MAP OF WEXFORD
 c. 1800

SKETCH MAP OF PREHISTORIC, DANISH & POST-NORMAN WEXFORD

PROMONTORY OF FORTH MOUNTAIN

Separating the deep river valleys of
BISHOP'S WATER and FARNOGUE rivers

Prehistoric Township Area

1. Ferry Boat Lane (Monck St)
2. Ferry Landing
3. Trumer Hamlet

Danish Township Area

4. Stockade/Castle Knoll
5. Danish Water Mill
6. St Patrick's Church
7. St Mary's ..
8. St Duloque's ..
9. Danish "Stone" Bridge
10. Peter's River (underground)

Early Extramural Churches

11. St Michael's
12. St Bride's
13. St Peter's
14. The Friary
15. St Iberius
16. St John & Brigid
17. St Selskar

Danish & Norman Gates

18. Castle Gate
19. Bride's Gate
20. Peter's Gate
21. Kayser Gate
22. Danish Market Gate
23. John's Gate
- West Gate

Post-Norman

24. Upper King St
25. Bride St Church
26. Roche's Road
27. Rowe St Church
28. Market House & Assembly Rooms
29. Old Court House
30. Bullring
31. Henrietta St.
32. Allen St
33. Rowe St
34. Church Lane
35. Common Quay St
36. Common Quay Reef
37. Charlotte St
38. County Hall (Court House 1805-192)
39. Railway Station North
40. Slaney St
41. Municipal Buildings
42. Kenny's Hall (Woolworths)
43. Norman Bridgehead Defences
44. Trumer Castle
45. John's Gate St

LEGEND

- Prehistoric Trails — — — — —
- Danish town boundary — — — — —
- Norman town boundary — — — — —
- Present day Streets — — — — —
- Danish Streets — — — — —
- Quay embankment — — — — —
- Old waterfront — — — — —
- Stepping rock — — — — —
- Marsh — — — — —
- Gates — — — — —
- Prehistoric Churches — — — — —

I. ANTIQUE SKETCH MAP.
J. W. H. S. VOL. I.

Drawn by V. Staples

3 WEXFORD 05 1840

1841

ST. MARY'S
ST. PATRICK'S
ST. MICHAEL'S
ST. JOHN'S
ST. GEORGE'S

WEXFORD

ST. MICHAEL'S

ST. JOHN'S

WEXFORD NORTH

St. Michael's

St. John's

St. Peter's College

St. George's

St. Michael's

St. John's

St. George's

1840 SUEVEN
REVISED 1921-22

Now Bridge
Drawbridge

FERRYBANK
(Crossing)

North Westford Station
Landing Stage

ST. PETER'S COLLEGE

ST. MICHAEL'S

CROWWELLS FORT

WHITEROCK SOUTH T.P. 100

MULGANNON T.P. 100

1840
REV. 1921-22